

The academe as the source of research and the knowledge utilization uptake in the health care system

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ABSTRACT

This descriptive-correlational research determined the relationship between the perceived level of the characteristics of the academe as the source of research and the knowledge utilization uptake of the academic research among health care professionals in the health care systems. Researcher-made questionnaire was used consisting of items related to credibility, accuracy, reasonableness, support, sophistication and communication quality was also employed. Moreover, an adapted questionnaire from the Knowledge Utilization Uptake Scale was used. The overall level of the perceived characteristics of the source in terms of the credibility, accuracy, reasonableness, support, sophistications and communication quality was fair. Generally, a very poor level of knowledge utilization uptake of the academic research was identified. Respondents were highly aware of the research but very poor in the aspects of reception, cognition, discussion, reference, effort, adoption and impact. Pearson r revealed a strong positive correlation between the variables. Finally, the perceived level on the characteristics of the source of the health research was associated with the knowledge utilization uptake. Hence, this contributed to the theory on the research translation from the academe to the health care system that source was an influential element.

Keywords: characteristics of source, academic health research, utilization, research knowledge

Worldwide, the idea of where the research information comes from has gained increasing interest to many potential users in many fields. The Southwest Educational Development Laboratory (SEDL) in 2008 emphasized that source of the information must be considered in developing knowledge-based that underlies utilization. Hence, it is one of the five common core elements to success. Furthermore, this source can strongly influence the effectiveness of the utilization

of the information. In the study, the academe is considered the source of information. The health research is conducted as a requirement before finishing a degree. As the production of academic health research, the new knowledge developed must improve the health profession. Hence, source credibility of the health research knowledge has become a common issue.

The Trustees of Columbia University in the City of New York (2013) mentioned that utilization of references is a means of supporting

the argument made that means references need to be credible and authoritative. In addition, SEDL (2008) argued that the source producing research outcomes to more important than the quality of the research design. Similarly, authors trust references with credible stand. Lastly, the source must necessarily possess these characteristics ideal for use among potential users that will improve the quality of health care service delivery.

Since source credibility is the extent to which a recipient perceives a source to be trustworthy and an expert, in previous knowledge transfer research, trust and reputation of a knowledge source collectively define a source's credibility (Joshi et al., 2004; Ko et al., 2005). In addition, Cook (2013) suggested that in the legal realm, to decide credibility, health care professionals must choose any of the following glitches, if present, whether they are serious: improbabilities, implausibilities, impossibilities, contradictions and inconsistencies. Desberg and Fisher (1998) identified criteria used to evaluate credibility such as breadth, depth, time, format, content and accuracy. Similarly, evaluating a physical information source can be done even before having the physical item in hand.

In addition, Gilbert, Fiske and Lindzey (1998) noted that there were other factors embraces a person's credibility but, according to source credibility theory, the two factors most regularly recognized were perceived expertise, and trustworthiness of the references. Furthermore, source credibility theory research also indicated that the capacity to adopt the message is subjective to receiver's understanding. Hence, Beebe (2005) added that credibility is considered as the capability of the believer whom he had conversed. Health care professionals can also appraise a source by first examining the bibliographic citation. Bibliographic citations' components can help determine the usefulness of this source for the paper (Cornell University Library, 2010).

With the current understanding of the academe as the source of information, the

study argued that a connection exists between the uniqueness of the source— those involved in the production of research knowledge in the academe and the utilization of research knowledge in the health care system in terms of the credibility, accuracy, reasonableness, support, sophistications and communication quality of the source. By considering the characteristics of the academe as the source of research information, this can potentially improve the knowledge utilization uptake in the health care system which can in turn improve the health care practice.

II. THE PROBLEM

The study determined the relationship between the characteristics of the academe as the source of the health research and the knowledge utilization uptake of the academic health research in the health care system. Specifically, it answered the following questions:

1. What is the characteristic of the academe as the source of the health research in terms of:
 - 1.1 credibility;
 - 1.2 accuracy;
 - 1.3 reasonableness;
 - 1.4 support;
 - 1.5 sophistications; and
 - 1.6 communication quality?;
2. What is the knowledge utilization uptake of the academic health research in the health care system?; and
3. Is there a significant relationship between the characteristics of the academe as the source of the health research and the knowledge utilization uptake of the academic health research in the health care system?

III. METHODOLOGY

Descriptive-correlational research design was used to determine the perceived characteristics of the academe as the source of the health research and the knowledge utilization uptake among health care

professionals in the health care system. Subsequently, relationship between the perceived characteristics of the academe as the source of the health research and the knowledge utilization uptake among health care professionals in the health care system was also sought. A researcher-made questionnaire was used with six characteristic themes namely: credibility; accuracy; reasonableness; support; sophistications; and communication quality. This consisted of 31 items related to the six themes. Content validity was sought through Delphi technique and pilot testing of the tool was also done. Reliability testing revealed a Cronbach's alpha of 0.993. In addition, an adapted questionnaire from the Knowledge Utilization Uptake Scale (Bonin, 2007) was used to assess the knowledge utilization of the academic health research consisted of the different statements that determined the level of knowledge utilization from the university's health researches which consisted of 34 items. This consisted of 34 items related to the nine stages of knowledge utilization uptake. Content validity was sought through Delphi technique and pilot testing of the tool was also done. Reliability testing revealed a Cronbach's alpha of 0.993. Finally, descriptive and inferential statistics were used after the data were gathered, collated and encoded in MS excel.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The section presents the results on the levels of the perceived characteristics of the academe as the source of research knowledge and the knowledge utilization uptake of the academic health research among the 100 health care professionals which included the physicians and medical specialists, nurses, medical technologists, radiologic technologists, pharmacists, occupational and physical therapists and nutritionist-dietitians. Subsequently, the result on the relationship between the variables is also presented.

Level of the perceived characteristics of the academe as the source of research knowledge. Table 1 presents the level of perceived characteristics of the academe as the source of research knowledge. It is described in terms of its credibility, accuracy, reasonableness, support, sophistications, and communication quality.

Table 1. Level of the perceived characteristics of the academe as the source of research knowledge

Indicators	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	Interpretation
A: Credibility	1.92	.129	Fair
B: Accuracy	1.98	.155	Fair
C: Reasonableness	1.74	.164	Poor
D: Support	2.11	.049	Fair
E: Sophistications	2.12	.034	Fair
F: Communication Quality	2.09	.032	Fair
Grand Mean	1.98	.170	Fair

Note. $n=100$. Parameters: 1.0-1.75 Poor; 1.76-2.50 Fair; 2.51-3.25 Moderate; 3.26-4.0 High

As shown in table, the overall level of the perceived characteristics of the academe as the source of the research knowledge is fair. This is attributed to the fair results in relation to credibility, accuracy, support, sophistications and communication quality. Hence, the academe still needs to improve the areas related to the characteristics of the source to enhance knowledge utilization uptake of the health care professionals. In terms of the credibility, health care professionals should make a strong conclusions according on facts, proof of authenticity and reliability or credibility, believability which is very vital. Accurateness must be the target of the academe to guarantee that the information is truthful so that health care professionals perceived it useful for the knowledge utilization. Meanwhile, support must be addressed by the academe as this is concerned with the source and corroboration of the information. Finally,

communication quality must be considered by the academe to disseminate the findings of their research outputs.

The highest was noted in the aspect of fair sophistications. It is the quality of the academe as the source of the information which can be readily used or applied. The result is attributed to the fair research knowledge presented with appropriate information, information with rigor and research knowledge oriented toward the use or application from the source. Meanwhile, the lowest was related to the poor reasonableness. Hence, the academe as the source poorly developed objectivity and reasoned actions of the research knowledge. McGraw-Hill Higher Education (2003) stressed that the source such as the academe must establish reasonable, stable, factual, rational, no conflict of interest, absence of fallacies or slanted tone. This is directed towards references that manage the subject considerately and rationally and a truthful source. However, the present result still lacks sufficient reasonableness.

The present findings added to the argument made by Trustees of Columbia University in the City of New York (2013) that the utilization of references is a way of supporting the argument, meaning sources of reference need to be credible and authoritative which was only fairly achieved by the academe as the source of the research knowledge. In like manner, the findings also related with Gilbert, Fiske and Lindzey (1998) on the other factors that may involve a person's credibility and Beebe (2005) on the trustworthiness is characterized as the individual's ability to trust to one's honesty wherein the academe only fairly achieved this dimension.

With the results revealed in the study, it is noted that the academe as one of the sources needs to exert more effort to meet every criterion of the characteristics related to the source necessary for the effective knowledge utilization uptake. Even if they will not possess the highest standard of quality, they must address these areas to achieve evidence-based

practice in the health care system.

Level of knowledge utilization uptake of the academic research among health care professionals. Table 2 presents the level of the knowledge utilization uptake of the academic health research among health care professionals. It is presented in terms of the different stages of utilizing knowledge uptake that includes awareness, reception, cognition, discussion, reference, effort, adoption, implementation and impact.

Table 2. Level of knowledge utilization uptake of the academic research among health care professionals

Stages	<i>M</i>	<i>SD</i>	Interpretation
1. Awareness	3.93	.030	<i>High</i>
2. Reception	1.67	.622	<i>Very Poor</i>
3. Cognition	1.60	.037	<i>Very Poor</i>
4. Discussion	1.31	.035	<i>Very Poor</i>
5. Reference	1.24	.025	<i>Very Poor</i>
6. Effort	1.14	.014	<i>Very Poor</i>
7. Adoption	1.01	.005	<i>Very Poor</i>
8. Impact	1.00	.000	<i>Very Poor</i>
Grand Mean	1.44	.823	<i>Very Poor</i>

Note: n= 100. Parameters: 1.0-1.80 Very Poor; 1.81-2.60 Poor; 2.61-3.40 Moderate; 3.41-4.20 High; 4.21-5.0 Very High

As shown in the table, the health care professionals are highly aware of the academic health research. High awareness is attributed to the high perceived levels of the academic health research learnt existence. However, they are all very poor in the aspects of reception, cognition, discussion, reference, effort, adoption and impact, respectively. Generally, they have very poor level of knowledge utilization uptake of the academic research.

The findings support the theory developed through the deductive approach on the academic knowledge translation: knowledge translation involves series of stages in new knowledge creation and its impact. The nine stages built upon the previous stages are: awareness; reception or transmission; cognition; discussion, reference

effort; adoption; implementation and impact. In the same manner, every stage of knowledge utilization scale is measured differently. Moreover, every stage comparable to the previous stages in which factors are explainable on how potential intended beneficiaries climbs the heights of knowledge utilization. Knowledge utilization started in echelon of awareness to transmission or reception, transmission or reception to the echelon to that of cognition, from cognition to discussion, then discussion to reference, from reference to effort, from effort to adoption, adoption to implementation and finally, from implementation to impact on the perspectives of the health care professionals. The interactions of the influential elements identified have significant influence on the effectiveness of the whole knowledge translation process of the academic health research in the health care system. Hence, constant evaluation of the overall knowledge translation process is crucial in the effectiveness of the whole process to successfully have research and evidence-practice in the health care system. However, numerous barriers related to the identified elements must be dealt with accordingly as they are minimizing the likelihood of research knowledge utilization uptake and climbing echelon of the heights of knowledge utilization uptake.

Finally, a health care professional does not possess the attributes necessary to the knowledge utilization uptake of the academic health research and fail to climb the ladder of the stages. In addition, the findings contribute to the theory developed through deductive approach

on the knowledge translation from the academe to the health care system. Hence, the health care professionals should design effective ways to fully climb the ladder of knowledge utilization uptake specifically in the academic health research to advance service quality delivered to clientele.

Relationship between the perceived characteristics of the academe as the source and the knowledge utilization uptake among health care professionals in the health care system. Table 3 presents the relationship between the perceived characteristics of the academe as the source of research knowledge and the knowledge utilization uptake among health care professionals in the health care system.

As shown in the table, a Pearson product moment correlation was computed to determine the relationship between the perceived characteristics of the academe as the source of the health research and the knowledge utilization uptake among health care professionals in the health care system. There is a strong positive correlation between the variables. ($r = .730$, $n = 100$, $p < .05$). Hence, the null hypothesis is rejected. Thus, this indicates that the fair level of perceived characteristics of the academe as the source of health research is directly related to the very poor knowledge utilization uptake among health care professionals in the health care system. Hence, increase in the perceived characteristics of the academe as the source, the knowledge utilization uptake also increases. On the other hand, the decrease in the perceived characteristics of the academe as the source of the health research also results to significant

Table 3. Relationship between the perceived characteristics of the academe as the source and the knowledge utilization uptake of the Academic Health Research ($n=100$)

Variables	Computed Pearson correlation	p-value	Decision over Ho	Interpretation
Perceived Characteristics of the Academe as the Source and the Knowledge Utilization Uptake	.730	.000	Reject Ho	Significant Relationship

Note: Correlation is significant at the 0.05 level (2-tailed).

decreases in the knowledge utilization uptake among health care professionals in the health care system.

As affirmed, confidence and validity of knowledge foundation collectively defined references accuracy necessary for subsequent knowledge utilization (Joshi et al., 2004; Ko et al., 2005). In addition, it affirmed SEDL (2008) that individual's trust references with credible stand. Moreover, the present results indicated that the perceived characteristics of the academe as the source of the research knowledge had significant influence on the knowledge utilization uptake of the health care professionals. Hence, the result of the hypothesis testing contributed to the emergent theory on knowledge translation from the academe to the health care system through deductive approach. In addition, the favorable characteristics related to the perspective of the academe as the credible source of the research knowledge are also high. Thus, the academe must possess high levels of the characteristic themes namely: credibility; accuracy; reasonableness; support; sophistications; and communication quality to effect have greater chances of knowledge utilization uptake. However, constant evaluation characteristics must be done to ensure the favorableness for subsequent knowledge utilization uptake that in turn leads to successful knowledge translation.

Therefore, the health care professionals in the health care system should ask relevant questions regarding the credibility of the source as they are constantly surrounded with information. Hence, they must have the skill necessary to evaluate the credibility of the source of the research knowledge for subsequent utilization. Additionally, area of source credibility has very significant practical implications in the field of evidence-based practice in health. Lastly, the health care professionals should continually ask questions, follow up and reflect on the sources to help realize the credibility of the source for the subsequent knowledge utilization uptake of the research knowledge produced.

V. CONCLUSION

The academe as the source of research knowledge is associated with the knowledge utilization uptake of the health care professionals. Hence, the high credibility, accuracy, reasonableness, support, sophistications and communication quality demonstrated by the academe influenced the knowledge utilization uptake of academic research in the health care system. Finally, this indicates that the generated hypotheses contributed to the theory where the source is an influential element in the knowledge utilization uptake of the research from the academe to the health care system among health care professionals. Hence, we recommend that the administrators of the academe should find ways to enhance and sustain their high credibility, accuracy, reasonableness, support, sophistications and communication quality.

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